

AEROBIC PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, PROTECTION MOTIVATION, AND PHYSICAL PERFORMANCE AMONG MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN

Shallen O. Araneta, MAEd, Darwin D. Ofrin, EdD

College of Teacher Education-Graduate Studies and Applied Research, Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12699256>

ABSTRACT

In the middle-aged population, engaging in routine physical activity has been shown to enhance sleep quality, promote favourable mental health outcomes, and mitigate the likelihood of developing age-related illnesses. According to Dishman (2010), it has been observed that a significant proportion of middle-aged women who initiate exercise routines are prone to discontinuing their regimen, with a dropout rate of 50% within six months. As individuals age, a sedentary lifestyle may develop. The individual's physical capabilities and kinaesthetic abilities are subject to certain limitations. The research aimed to investigate the levels of aerobic physical activity, protection motivation, and physical performance in middle-aged women residing in Atimonan, Quezon. The study utilized descriptive research methodology. The research encompassed a sample of middle-aged individuals residing in Atimonan, Quezon. The study concluded that there was both a statistically insignificant and a significant correlation between the variables of aerobic physical activity and physical performance. A significant correlation was discovered between protection motivation and physical performance. It is advisable for prospective researchers to devise a physical fitness regimen tailored to middle-aged women. The survey may also encompass a diverse range of gender identities and age cohorts as participants.

Keywords: *Aerobic Physical Activity, Middle-aged Women, Protection Motivation, Physical Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Engagement in physical activity and exercise has been linked to various advantages throughout the lifespan of women in middle age, such as reduced susceptibility to cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, hypertension, depression, and osteoporosis (Warburton et al., 2016). It has been discovered that engaging in regular physical activity during middle age improves sleep quality, fosters mental health outcomes, and lowers the risk of certain age-related disorders. Due to the accompanying advantages, individuals should engage in frequent moderate-to-vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity (MVPA), such as walking, jogging, or cycling, according to the World Health Organization's "Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health." For adults to experience significant health benefits, the 2008 Guidelines recommend a minimum of 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity per week, 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity per week, or a comparable combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity physical activity (Foodconsumer.org, 2011). Despite the mounting evidence supporting the advantages of exercise and aerobic physical activity, statistics indicate that a significant proportion of the population, approximately 58%, remains inactive, as per the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) 1990 guidelines (United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 1993). According to Dishman (2010), it has been observed that even among middle-aged individuals who initiate exercise, there is a high probability of 50% of women discontinuing the activity within a period of 6 months.

A useful cognitive framework for comprehending people's motivation to engage in protective behaviours, such as exercise and physical activity, is provided by Rogers' 1975 Protection Motivation model. According to the protective motive hypothesis, four characteristics can be used to predict a person's intention to engage in a particular behaviour, such as exercise or physical activity. The perceived seriousness of the threat, which relates to the detrimental effects of aerobic physical inactivity, is one of these variables. Other significant predictors include perceived susceptibility to the danger, perceived benefits or effectiveness of the preventive behaviours, such as the effectiveness of exercise in enhancing health, and perceived self-efficacy, or confidence in one's capacity to carry out the advised behaviour, such as confidence in performing enough exercise to reap the benefits to health.

According to the Mayo Clinic (2020), engaging in aerobic physical activity is identified as another crucial factor for middle-aged women to achieve successful aging and maintain a healthy lifestyle. Several intervention studies have effectively utilized behavioural techniques to impact participation in physical activity. Studies on interventions typically indicate a rise in the frequency of aerobic physical activity, which can range from 10 to 25% (Mcauley & Lox, 2015). Irrespective of an individual's age, weight, or athletic capacity, engaging in aerobic activity that is appropriately intense, frequent, and of adequate duration is beneficial for one's health. Irrespective of one's age, engaging in aerobic activity can yield numerous health advantage.

Considering the protective advantages of exercise and aerobic physical activity in middle age, it is plausible that an intervention centered on information and aimed at enhancing protection motivation constructs could effectively influence the exercise and aerobic physical activity intentions of middle-aged individuals, leading to an initial change in behaviour (Gaston & Prapavessis, 2019).

In conclusion, as per the findings of a study conducted by Courneya (2015), there exists a significant correlation between perceived severity and both activity level and intention to exercise. Despite the existence of indirect evidence from previous studies of Biddle & Nigg (2016), there is a dearth of research that has directly examined the concept of protection motivation in the context of exercise and aerobic physical activity among middle-aged women. Additionally, it has been emphasized by Mcauley and Lox (2015) that the most reliable epidemiological estimates indicate that a minority of individuals between the ages of 18 and 65 engage in physical activity at an adequate level of intensity, frequency, and duration to achieve favourable health outcomes associated with exercise. Specifically, less than 20% of this population meets the recommended exercise guidelines. Regrettably, it is estimated that a sedentary lifestyle is prevalent among 30 to 59% of the middle-aged population. It is imperative to undertake this investigation specifically for middle-aged women, given that they are the demographic that participates in structured exercise or aerobic physical regimens but often discontinues such activities prior to reaping any associated health advantages. The attrition rate in exercise programs is a well-documented phenomenon, with statistics indicating that approximately 50% of participants discontinue their involvement within the initial six-month period.

The researcher wished to determine the level of aerobic physical activity, extent of protection motivation, and physical performance of sedentary, middle-aged adults through assessing the relationship of the variables being used in the study.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine aerobic physical activity, protection motivation, and physical performance among middle-aged women in Atimonan, Quezon.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following problem statements:

1. How do the respondents describe their level of aerobic physical activity in terms of:
 - 1.1 Frequency
 - 1.2 Intensity
 - 1.3 Duration
2. What is the extent of protection motivation among middle-aged women in terms of:
 - 2.1 Perceived Severity
 - 2.2 Perceived Vulnerability
 - 2.3 Perceived Benefits or Response Efficacy
 - 2.4 Self-Efficacy
3. How do the respondents perceive their physical performance as to:
 - 3.1 Body Movements
 - 3.2 Improve Functioning
 - 3.3 Enhanced Sound Mind

3.4 Good Body Mechanics

4. Is there any significant relationship between aerobic physical activity and the physical performance of middle-aged women?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the protection motivation and the physical performance of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the descriptive-correlational method of research was employed by the researcher to collect data pertaining to the current state of the investigation, as noted by Downs and Ulbrecht (2016). The researcher intended to determine the aerobic physical activity, protection motivation, and physical performance of middle-aged women and to ascertain if there is a significant relationship between the variables being used in the study. The researcher employed a purposive sampling method to select participants for the study. In this case, the researcher selected middle-aged adults in Atimonan, Quezon. It consisted of thirty (30) middle-aged adults from Brgy. Tagbakin, thirty (30) middle-aged adults from Brgy. Sapaan and forty (40) middle-aged adults from Brgy. San Isidro with a total number of one hundred (100) respondents. They are chosen since the study focus on the middle-aged women in the age bracket of 50 to 60 years.

The researcher employed the modified type of questionnaire (Corbin et al., 2019) to gather information on aerobic physical activity, protection motivation, and physical performance among the middle-aged people. The questionnaire is used as the main data gathering instrument for this study and it consisted of three parts. The first part contains the fill in response that pertains to the respondents' information about their name, age, gender, and address. The second part of the questionnaire is the survey indicating the questions relating to the level of aerobic physical activity includes intensity, frequency, and duration. The third part comprises the extent of protection motivation that deals with the perceived severity, perceived vulnerability, perceived benefits, and self-efficacy. The last part is the physical performance of the respondents in terms of body movements, improve functioning, enhance sound mind, and good body mechanics.

The questionnaire is written in English. The item in the questionnaire is rated into Likert-scale type. Upon receiving approval from the research adviser and undergoing evaluation by multiple panels of experts to ensure content quality, the researcher proceeded to conduct a study on the relationship between aerobic physical activity, protection motivation, and physical performance among middle-aged women in Atimonan, Quezon. This study utilized quantitative research methodologies. The proposed duration for the research timeline is between one and two months.

The researcher formulated a questionnaire as the main instrument. The data that gathered in this research study are from individual people, the middle-aged. The collection of data is subject to the level of aerobic physical activity, extent of protection motivation, and physical performance of middle-aged adults. After implementation, the researcher will compile all the instruments and gather all the needed data.

After checking, the middle-aged women's responses were summarized by the researcher and forwarded to his statistician for statistical treatment. After the results from the statistician, an analysis of data will be done.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Aerobic Physical Activity in terms of Frequency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Aerobic Physical Activity (E.G. Swimming, Jogging, Aerobics, Basketball, Or Workout)	2.37	1.522	1-2days/week
2. Walking/Cycling, Including Walking To Work, Shopping, Or For Pleasure.	3.33	1.551	1 days/week
3. Housework (Cleaning Floors, Washing Dishes, Cooking)	4.44	1.113	4-5 days/week
4. Caring For Relatives Who Need Help (Has Chronic Illness) Or Nursing For Children	3.44	1.641	1 days/week
5. Farming Or Gardening	3.12	1.584	3 days/week
Overall Mean	3.34	1.482	3 days/week

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 Almost everyday; 3.50 - 4.49 4-5 days/week; 2.50 - 3.49 3 days/week; 1.50 - 2.49 1-2 days/week ; 1.00 - 1.49 Never

Table 2. Level of Aerobic Physical Activity in terms of Intensity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Running, jogging, swimming, Zumba, or Bicycling	2.31	1.22	Light
2. Heavy housework (e.g. digging, refitting a kitchen/bathroom)	3.33	1.48	Moderate
3. Heavy manual (e.g. moving heavy furniture, cleaning windows)	2.92	1.34	Moderate
4. Walking to and from work, and all other walking done for recreation, sport, and exercise, or leisure.	2.88	1.47	Moderate
5. Farming	2.84	1.48	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.86	1.40	Moderate

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 Very Hard; 3.50 - 4.49 Hard; 2.50 - 3.49 Moderate; 1.50 - 2.49 Light; 1.00 - 1.4 Very Light

Table 3. Level of Aerobic Physical Activity in terms of Duration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Running, jogging, swimming, Zumba, or Bicycling	2.50	1.42	60 – 90 minutes
2. Heavy housework (e.g. digging, refitting a kitchen/bathroom)	2.28	1.33	30 – 60 minutes
3. Heavy manual (e.g. moving heavy furniture, cleaning windows)	2.15	1.31	30 – 60 minutes
4. Walking to and from work, and all other walking done for recreation, sport, and exercise, or leisure.	3.60	1.42	60 – 90 minutes
5. Farming	2.50	1.49	60 – 90 minutes
Overall Mean	2.61	1.40	60 – 90 minutes

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 More than 120 minutes; 3.50 - 4.49 90-120 minutes; 2.50 - 3.49 60-90 minutes; 1.50 - 2.49 30-60 minutes; 1.00 - 1.49 Less than 30 minutes

Table 4. Extent of Protection Motivation in terms of Perceived Severity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Getting heart disease by not doing physical activity would be a very bad thing to happen to me.	2.80	0.93	Agree
2. Not engaging in physical activity will lead me to sedentary lifestyle.	2.68	0.85	Agree
3. I am at risk of having osteoporosis and other bone/muscle problems due to physical inactivity.	2.37	0.91	Disagree
4. It feels a little stiff or sore whenever I perform physical activity.	2.46	0.80	Agree
5. The disease caused by physical inactivity is a bigger threat to me than to most people.	2.66	0.90	Agree
Overall Mean	2.59	0.88	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 5. *The extent of Protection Motivation in terms of Perceived Vulnerability*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I fear of falling while doing physical activity.	2.64	0.86	Agree
2. If I don't get physical activity, I would be at risk for serious health problem.	2.83	0.85	Agree
3. I am too exhausted in doing physical activity.	2.53	0.75	Agree
4. I can't notice any improvement in fitness.	2.32	0.82	Disagree
5. I don't have secure environment to be physically active.	2.47	0.86	Disagree
Overall Mean	2.56	0.83	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 6. *The extent of Protection Motivation in terms of Perceived Benefits or Response Efficacy*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity will help me get physically fit.	3.40	0.67	Agree
2. Physical activity will reduce my chances of getting serious health problems.	3.20	0.78	Agree
3. I will live longer if I am physically active.	3.38	0.69	Agree
4. Physical activity improves my mental health.	3.38	0.74	Agree
5. Physical activity helps me sleep better at night.	3.29	0.66	Agree
Overall Mean	3.33	0.71	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 7. *Extent of Protection Motivation in terms of Self-Efficacy*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity helps me to have a more positive outlook in life.	3.33	0.62	Agree
2. Physical activity makes me feel better in general.	3.30	0.69	Agree

3. Physical activity improves my balance and flexibility.	3.33	0.67	Agree
4. Physical activity lets me keep in contact with friends.	3.18	0.66	Agree
5. Physical activity is fun for me.	3.28	0.81	Agree
Overall Mean	3.28	0.69	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 8. Perception of Physical Performance as to Body Movement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity increases my muscle strength.	3.34	0.61	Agree
2. Physical activity increases my level of physical fitness.	3.35	0.61	Agree
3. Muscle tone is improved with physical activity.	3.34	0.67	Agree
4. Physical activity helps me decrease fatigue.	3.06	0.66	Agree
5. My physical endurance is improved by doing physical activity.	3.20	0.62	Agree
Overall Mean	3.26	0.63	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 9. Perception on Physical Performance as to Improve Functioning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity improves my stamina.	3.25	0.67	Agree
2. Physical activity improves the functioning of my cardiovascular system.	3.20	0.67	Agree
3. Physical activity allows me to carry out normal activities without becoming tired.	3.19	0.66	Agree
4. Physical activity improves my quality of work.	3.19	0.69	Agree
5. Physical activity improves overall body functioning for me.	3.38	0.62	Agree
Overall Mean	3.24	0.66	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 10. Perception on Physical Performance as to Enhanced Sound Mind

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity helps me sleep better at night.	3.29	0.67	Agree
2. Physical activity improves my self-concept.	3.24	0.59	Agree
3. Physical activity increases my mental alertness.	3.14	0.67	Agree
4. Physical activity helps me cope with stress.	3.19	0.71	Agree
5. Physical activity sharpens my mind.	3.12	0.71	Agree
Overall Mean	3.20	0.67	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 11. Perception of Physical Performance as to Good Body Mechanics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Physical activity improves my flexibility.	3.32	0.66	Agree
2. Physical activity helps reduce the risk of injury e.g. fall.	3.08	0.66	Agree
3. Physical activity delays the onset of major disability.	2.95	0.78	Agree
4. Physical activity helps strengthen my bone structure.	3.19	0.72	Agree
5. Physical activity improves my balance.	3.31	0.68	Agree
Overall Mean	3.17	0.70	Agree

Legend: 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 - 3.49 Agree; 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 12. Relationship between Aerobic Physical Activity and Physical Performance

Aerobic Physical Activity	Physical Performance of Middle-aged Women			
	Body Movements	Improve Functioning	Enhanced Sound Mind	Good Body Mechanics
Frequency	0.237*	0.132	0.266**	0.280**
Intensity	0.177	0.213*	0.321**	0.232*
Duration	0.202*	0.076	0.166	0.130

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Coefficients: .90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00) Very high positive (negative) correlation; .70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90) High positive (negative) correlation; .50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70) Moderate positive (negative) correlation; .30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50) Low positive (negative) correlation; and .00 to .30 (.00 to -.30) Negligible correlation**

Table 13. Relationship between Protection Motivation and Physical Performance

Protection Motivation	Physical Performance			
	Body Movements	Improve Functioning	Enhanced Sound Mind	Good Body Mechanics
Perceived Severity	0.410**	0.338**	0.515**	0.449**
Perceived Vulnerability	0.214*	0.184	0.289**	0.296**
Perceived Benefits or Response Efficacy	0.703**	0.699**	0.762**	0.709**
Self-Efficacy	0.688**	0.599**	0.665**	0.614**

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Coefficients: .90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00) Very high positive (negative) correlation; .70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90) High positive (negative) correlation; .50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70) Moderate positive (negative) correlation; .30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50) Low positive (negative) correlation; and .00 to .30 (.00 to -.30) Negligible correlation**

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the middle-aged women’s level of aerobic physical activity as to frequency. The following are the descriptors of frequency: never, 1-2 days/week-rarely, 3 days/week-sometimes, 4-5 days/week-frequent, and almost every day or very frequent. The respondents obtained the highest mean of 4.44 with a 1.113 standard deviation, which was interpreted as 4 – 5 days/week on the 3rd indicator. Given that most of the respondents are housewives, they frequently engaged mostly in housework (Cleaning Floors, Washing Dishes, Cooking). On the other hand, indicator 1, Aerobic Physical Activity (e.g., swimming, jogging, aerobics, basketball, or workout), obtained the lowest mean of 2.37 with 1.522, which was interpreted as 1 -2 days/week. The middle-aged women are rarely performing aerobic physical activity since their residence is in a barrio and probably their location doesn’t have a proper amenity. On average, the respondents performed the indicated aerobic physical activities for 3 days/week. It means that they engage in aerobic physical activity sometimes. However, to gain maximum benefits from aerobic physical activity, 3-5 days a week is best. Aerobic exercise has short-term psychological and physiological benefits, thus it's important to exercise often to maintain these advantages. According to research from the Centers for Disease Control, the Michigan Department of Community Health examined data from the 1996 and 1998

BRFSS and discovered that just 1 in 18 adults who identified walking as their primary form of exercise were getting enough exercise (Cooper, 2011).

Table 2 presents the middle-aged women's level of aerobic physical activity as to intensity. The respondents perceived the highest mean of 3.33 on indicator 2 (Heavy housework) with a standard deviation of 1.48 and an interpretation of moderate. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 2.31 with a 1.22 standard deviation and interpretation of light is on indicator 1 (Running, jogging, swimming, Zumba, or Bicycling). The overall mean was 2.86. This implies that the respondents performed moderate levels of aerobic physical activities. Empirical evidence suggests that engaging in high-intensity exercise may lead to an increase in stress levels rather than a reduction. Therefore, it is recommended to refrain from exceeding 80% of one's maximum heart rate. Optimal results can be achieved by engaging in moderate-intensity exercise, which typically involves maintaining a heart rate of approximately 60% of one's maximum capacity, considering individual age and circumstances. According to Cooper (2011), empirical evidence suggests that exercising at 50–60% of one's maximum heart rate yields similar advantageous outcomes as exercising at an intensity of 80% of one's maximum heart rate.

Table 3 presents the middle-aged women's levels of aerobic physical activity as to duration. Most of the indicators were described within 60-90 minutes with an overall mean of 2.61. It is depicted that the respondents' duration in aerobic physical activity is within 60-90 minutes. The following are the descriptors of duration: less than 30 minutes-not achieved, 30-60 minutes-slightly achieved, 60-90 minutes-moderately achieved, 90-120 minutes-achieved, and more than 120 minutes- highly achieved. Additionally, respondents believed that indication 4 had the highest mean of 3.60, the smallest standard deviation of 1.42, and the longest interpretation range of 60 to 90 minutes (Walking to and from work, and all other walking done for recreation, sport, exercise, or leisure). Since several of the respondents live close to the school where their kids go, especially during the week, they only moderately met the duration goal. Indicator 3 obtained the lowest mean of 2.15 with a 1.31 standard deviation and an interpretation of 30 to 60 minutes (Heavy manual). They barely met this criterion, perhaps because there aren't many middle-aged males participating in this activity for them. It is advised that middle-aged women who exercise get a minimum of 150 minutes of moderate aerobic activity, 75 minutes of strenuous aerobic activity, or a combination of both levels each week. It is advised to spread out this exercise over the course of a week, per the instructions. Higher levels of physical activity are linked to better health outcomes. Physical activity of any intensity is helpful. Short bursts of physical activity spread throughout the day might add up to positive health effects (Laskowski, 2021).

The data presented in Table 4 shows the middle-aged women's extent of protection motivation in terms of perceived severity. Assessment has an overall mean of 2.59 and indicator 1 "Getting heart disease by not doing physical activity would be a very bad thing to happen to me" has the highest mean of 2.80 with a standard deviation of 0.93 and interpretation of agree which implies that the respondents agreed that there was a protection motivation among middle-aged women in terms of perceived severity. The

respondents protect themselves from the severity of threats associated with physical inactivity, which is why they are motivated to perform aerobic physical activity. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 2.80 with a standard deviation of 0.93 and interpretation of agreement obtained by indicator 3 (I am at risk of having osteoporosis and other bone/muscle problems due to physical inactivity). Typically, some instances are viewed as more dangerous than others (such as a myocardial infarction brought on by inactivity) (a pound too much body weight for an intermediate time). The greater the health danger, the more probable it is that a motivation will arise, and a suggested activity will be adopted (Courneya, 2015).

The data presented in Table 5 shows a summary of middle-aged women's extent of protection motivation in terms of perceived vulnerability. The respondents perceived the highest mean of 2.83 with 0.85 standard deviation on the second indicator which tells that if middle-aged women don't get physical activity, they would be at risk for serious health problems. Meanwhile, indicator 4 has the lowest mean of 2.32 which says that the respondents disagreed that they can't notice any improvement in fitness. They may disagree because they are not consistent in performing aerobic physical activity. Moreover, most indicators fall under Agree Level which indicates that the middle-aged women agreed that they are protected from risks since they are engaged in aerobic physical activity.

Table 6 presents the extent of protection motivation in terms of perceived benefits. The respondents' perceived the highest mean of 3.40 on indicator 1 (Physical activity will help me get physically fit.) with a standard deviation of 0.67. However, indicator 2 obtained the lowest mean of 3.20 (Physical activity will reduce my chances of getting serious health problems). This shows that they agreed with the benefits of aerobic physical activity because it improves their mental health, helps them to be physically fit, and sleep better at night. According to Kotecki and Thomas (2017), scholarly investigations have concurred that engaging in exercise and physical activity can be advantageous for individuals of all ages and can facilitate the enhancement of their overall health and daily routine.

Table 7 shows the middle-aged women's extent of protection motivation in terms of self-efficacy. The respondents perceived the highest mean of 3.33 on the 1st and 3rd indicators which shows that the respondents agreed that physical activity helps them to have a more positive outlook in life and it improves their balance and flexibility. On the other hand, indicator 4 (Physical activity lets me keep in contact with friends.) obtained the lowest mean of 3.18. This indicates that they are too far from their friends since they live in a barrio. All indicators fall under the Agree category with an overall mean of 3.28. It means that they have self-efficacy when they perform such activities since it improves their balance and flexibility, makes them feel better in general, and have a positive outlook in life. According to Kotecki and Thomas (2017), physical activity can exert a favorable influence on both our physical appearance and our self-perception of it. Robust and sturdy musculature enables improved body alignment and a distinct elegance in locomotion. The maintenance of muscular fitness is a crucial factor in promoting a positive perception of one's physical appearance.

Table 8 presents middle-aged women's perception of their physical performance. The respondents perceived the highest mean of 3.35 on indicator 2 (Physical activity increases my level of physical fitness) with a standard deviation of 0.61 and an interpretation of agree. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.06 with a 0.66 standard deviation and interpretation of agree is on indicator 4 (Physical activity helps me decrease fatigue). The overall mean was 3.26. This describes that the respondents are physically performing since they agreed that they increase muscle strength, and physical fitness and improved their physical endurance.

Table 9 presents middle-aged women's perception of physical performance in terms of improved functioning. All indicators fall under the Agree category with an overall mean of 3.24. It is depicted that the respondents have physical performance since it shows that it improves their body function in general. Furthermore, the respondents perceived the highest mean of 3.38 with a standard deviation of 0.62 and interpretation of agree on indicator 5 (Physical activity improves overall body functioning for me). Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.19 with 0.66 and 0.69 standard deviation and interpretation of agree was obtained by indicator 3 and 4 (Physical activity allows me to carry out normal activities without becoming tired and Physical activity improves my quality of work).

The data presented on table 10 shows the middle-aged women's perception of physical performance in terms of enhanced sound mind. Assessment has an overall mean of 3.20 and indicator 1 "Physical activity helps me sleep better at night" has the highest mean of 3.29 with a standard deviation of 0.67 and interpretation of agree which implies that the respondents agreed that they are physically performing because physical activity helps them cope with stress and sharpens their mind. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.12 with a standard deviation of 0.71 and interpretation of agree obtained by indicator 5 (Physical activity sharpens my mind).

The data presented in Table 11 shows a summary of middle-aged women's perception of physical performance in terms of good body mechanics. The first indicator, which indicates that physical exercise enhances the respondents' flexibility, received the highest mean rating from the respondents—3.32 with a 0.66 standard deviation. The respondents believed that physical activity prevents the onset of significant disability, and indication 3 has the lowest mean of 2.95. Moreover, most indicators fall under Agree Level which indicates that the middle-aged women agreed that they are performing physically because they have achieved good body mechanics. The concept of body mechanics pertains to the synchronized functioning of the musculoskeletal system and the nervous system to uphold equilibrium, stance, and arrangement while carrying out activities such as mobilizing, relocating, and orienting patients. According to Perry et al., (2014), the implementation of appropriate body mechanics enables individuals to perform tasks with minimal exertion and reduces the likelihood of injuries for both patients and healthcare practitioners.

Table 12 presents that the following indicators for aerobic physical activity and physical performance of middle-aged women have a *very weak relationship*: frequency and improve functioning ($r=0.132$), intensity and body movement ($r=0.177$), duration and

improving functioning ($r=0.076$), and duration and good body mechanics ($r=0.130$). At 0.05 level of significance, the two variables *have no significant relationship* with each other. It just shows that middle-aged women are not physically performing since in aerobic physical activity, middle-aged women should perform at least 150 minutes a week to have a greater health benefit. On the other hand, the physical performance of middle-aged women obtained a *weak relationship*: frequency and body movements ($r=0.237$), frequency and enhanced Sound Mind($r=0.266$), frequency and good body mechanics ($r=0.280$), intensity and improve functioning ($r=0.213$), intensity and enhanced sound mind ($r=0.321$), intensity and good body mechanics ($r=0.232$), and duration and body movements ($r=0.202$). At 0.05 level of significance, each variable had a *significant relationship* with each other. It implies that the respondents are physically performing because it is ideal to perform aerobic physical activity within 3 days/week and engaged in moderate intensity aerobic activity.

Table 13 shows that the computed r-value also indicated that protection motivation in terms of perceived severity, perceived benefits, and self-efficacy, have a significant relationship to each indicator for physical performance at 0.05 level of significance. However, even though the degree of relationship is weak, the computed r-value indicated that protection motivation in terms of perceived vulnerability had a significant relationship to each indicator for physical performance at 0.05 level of significance except for improved functioning. This shows that middle-aged women protect themselves from the severity of threats and risk which is why they are motivated to engage in aerobic physical activity that makes them physically performing.

Conclusions

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the conclusion: (1) Since it was found out that there was insignificant and significant relationship existed between and among the variables of aerobic physical activity and physical performance, then the null hypothesis is partially sustained; and (2) Given that there was a significant relationship existed between and among the variables of protection motivation and physical performance, the null hypothesis is not sustained.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: (1) For future researchers, they may create a fitness plan for middle-aged women. They may also involve other genders and age group as respondents; and (2) For the Local Health Officers, they can make the result of the study as a springboard in engaging middle-aged adults in aerobic physical activities where they can be productive and improve their fitness. This will also provide meaningful data for the

improvement of their municipality in terms of projects, programs, and activities that will be implemented in middle-aged women.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare compliance in ethical standard. All respondents gave their informed consent for inclusion before they participated in the study. Their anonymity has been observed as well. No conflict or harm has been done in gathering data. Proper citation of related literature and studies are maintained. More importantly, there is no bias or prejudice in the findings and results of this study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher is very grateful to God Almighty for the wisdom, strength, and good health bestowed upon her to accomplish her research. Immeasurable appreciation and deepest gratitude for guidance and support are extended to the family of the researcher and to Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus.

REFERENCES

- Biddle, S. and Nigg, C. R. (2016). Physical activity and mental health: evidence is growing. *World Psychiatry* 15(2), P176-P177.
- Cooper, R. et al., (2011). Physical Activity Across Adulthood and Physical Performance in Midlife.
- Courneya, K.S. (2015). Top 10 Research Questions Related to Physical Activity and Cancer Survivorship. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 86(2), 107-116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2015.991265>.
- Dishman, R.K. Working out boosts brain health. 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/topics/exercise-fitness/stress>
- Downs, D. and Ulbrecht J. (2016). Understanding Exercise Beliefs and Behaviors in Women With Gestational Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes Care* 29:236–240. Vol. 29, No. 2
- Gaston, A. and Prapavessis H. (2019). Using a combined protection motivation theory and health action process approach intervention to promote exercise during pregnancy. *Health Psychology* 28(6):726-33
- Laskowski, E.R. (expert opinion). How much should the average adult exercise every day?. *Health Lifestyle Fitness*. Mayo Clinic; 2021.
- Mcauley, E. and Lox, C. (2015). Long-term maintenance of exercise, self-efficacy, and physiological change in older adults. *Journal of gerontology*, 48(4), P218-P224.
- United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (1993). A recommendation from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and the American

College of Sports Medicine. JAMA The Journal of the American Medical Association 273(5): 402-407.

Warburton D.E. et al., (2016). Reflections on Physical Activity and Health: What Should We Recommend?. *The Canadian journal of cardiology*, 32(4), 495-504.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjca.2016.01.024>